

**OF MILITARY SERVANTS OF ENGINEERING TROOPS
PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITY OF DEVELOPING MECHANISMS FOR
IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION**

Jabbarov Zarifboy Rustamovich

Military National University of Uzbekistan

teacher of the training center, associate professor, lieutenant colonel

Annotatsiya. Maqolada muhandislik qo'shinlari harbiy xizmatchilarining ta'lim sifatini takomillashtirish mexanizmlarini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslarini yaratishni muhim pedagogik muammo sifatida qarash mumkin. Muhandislik qo'shinlari harbiy xizmatchilarining vazifalarini to'laqonli bajarilishi, chinakam vatanparvarlar, o'z ishining malakali mutaxassislaridan iborat professional armiya vakillarini yetishtirish imkonini beradi. Bunday jiddiy, o'ta mas'uliyatli va sharaflil vazifani uddalashda oliy harbiy ta'lim muassasalaridagi muhandislik qo'shinlari harbiy xizmatchilarining tayyorgarligi muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: mudofaa, Qurolli Kuchlar, ta'im, ta'lim sifatini takomillashtirish mexanizmlari, harbiy xizmatchilar, muhandislik qo'shinlari, samaradorlik.

Аннотация. В статье создание научно-теоретической основы для разработки механизмов повышения качества образования военнослужащих инженерных войск можно рассматривать как важную педагогическую задачу. Полноценное выполнение обязанностей военнослужащими инженерных войск позволяет подготовить профессиональных представителей армии, состоящих из истинных патриотов и квалифицированных специалистов своего дела. Подготовка военнослужащих инженерных войск в высших военных образовательных учреждениях имеет важное значение для выполнения столь серьезной, весьма ответственной и почетной задачи.

Ключевые слова: оборона, Вооруженные Силы, продовольствие, механизмы повышения качества образования, военнослужащие, инженерные войска, эффективность.

Annotation. In the article, the creation of a scientific and theoretical basis for the development of mechanisms for improving the quality of education of engineering troops can be considered as an important pedagogical task. The full performance of duties by military personnel of the engineering troops allows us to prepare professional representatives of the army, consisting of true patriots and qualified specialists in their field. The training of engineering troops in higher

military educational institutions is important for the performance of such a serious, very responsible and honorable task.

Key words: defense, Armed Forces, food, mechanisms for improving the quality of education, military personnel, engineering troops, and efficiency.

Principal approaches to Uzbekistan's defense policy, the basis of their application, the tasks facing the Armed Forces, as well as promising directions for the continuation of the construction and development of our national army have been determined and are being implemented today.

The head of state and the relevant nomenclature structures pay great attention to the unconditional implementation of the tasks defined in the defense doctrine. Taking into account the provisions of the defense doctrine and the geostrategic location of our country, the structural structure and tasks of the military districts have been fundamentally revised. In particular, the structural structure of all associations and parts of the Ministry of Defense has been completely updated. We pay special attention to the readiness of the units to fully engage in combat training, to improve the professional skills of military personnel and to accurately perform tasks in their field. In addition, every officer and sergeant must ask, "Am I fit to continue in the future?" must answer the question, - says President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.

In addition, the world experience of the development of higher military education shows that in almost all developed countries of the world, the issues of improving the quality of education of military personnel of engineering troops [1] are not resolved and require in-depth research. Also, the training of servicemen of the engineering troops should be aimed at developing their ability to think more unusually, objectively and creatively, to make the right decisions, and to ensure the rapid development of the field of professional activity.

With the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Development of New Uzbekistan in 2022-2026" 100 goals within the seven priority areas of development of Uzbekistan

Important works on implementation have been defined for 5 years [2].

The new Uzbekistan demands to bring the effectiveness of education of military personnel in the spirit of national patriotism and high spiritual and moral values to a new level, to further increase the activity of higher military educational institutions in this direction, to instill in their minds feelings of courage.

The solution to this problem is to increase the effectiveness of educational work in higher military educational institutions, to create a horizontal and vertical system of education and morals of military personnel and to educate them in national patriotism, to instill universal and national values into the hearts and minds of

military personnel. by inculcating national patriotic, loyal and ambitious military personnel from the period of study in educational institutions to become the children of the new Uzbekistan, to make them strong spiritual, independent thinkers, who take responsibility for the fate and future of the Motherland, training of military personnel who will protect the interests of the state and society, fight valiantly against ignorance with enlightenment; educating military personnel based on the sacrifices of the nation who fought for the freedom and education of our people, who were not indifferent to the fate of the Motherland and the people; It is determined to educate military personnel in the spirit of national patriotism and a holistic, unified, scientific-based complex methodology of spiritual-educational, educational work based on a differential approach.

In this process, the development of the culture of military personnel, universal and national values, the reforms implemented in the new Uzbekistan, legal and economic literacy, and the formation of a modern outlook on active citizenship; the history of our great country, the rich spiritual and educational heritage of our great ancestors Abu Raykhan Beruni, Al Farghani, Alisher Navoi, Amir Temur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Mirza Ulugbek, their contributions to world civilization wide promotion among employees; law enforcement agencies in forming in military personnel the skills to approach the processes taking place in the world based on our national interests and a healthy outlook against malicious information, harmful vices, and destructive ideas spread through the Internet global information network organization on the basis of a plan; in the process of educating military personnel in the spirit of national patriotism, regardless of nationality, language and religion, social education aimed at forming a sense of loyalty to the Motherland in them, educating them as individuals capable of fulfilling their civil duties and constitutional obligations, protecting the interests of society and the state - organization of legal, ideological-ideological, spiritual-educational and physical-educational activities; In order to educate military personnel in the spirit of national patriotism in higher military educational institutions, "Three Generation Meetings" are systematically held with dedicated individuals and veterans with rich life experience, winners of various competitions and contests in the fields of science, culture and sports. to pass; "Most advanced specialist", "Outstanding military serviceman" in educational institutions that carry out activities aimed at forming and developing the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland during the education and training of military personnel conducting contests; it is recommended to be based on several principles and approaches in the process of public, cultural, educational and educational work.

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Principles such as continuity, harmony of education and upbringing, scientificity, historicity, coherence, consistency of the educational process, as well as individual approach, competence approach, acmeological approach, axiological approach, systematic approach, person-oriented approaches. The methods of educating military personnel in the spirit of national patriotism are aimed at forming in them the necessary life knowledge, skills, skills and strong will, high spiritual and moral qualities, and this, first of all, affects their mind, spirit and activity. Based on the external and internal factors, the following methods of training are defined: in the process of training military personnel in the spirit of national patriotism, the organization of spiritual and cultural events with representatives of culture and famous military personnel, question and answer evenings, presentations, seminars and trainings. , organizing debates, quizzes, roundtable discussions.

In this process, effective organization through the use of mass media, websites, Telegram, Instagram, Facebook and other informational tools; it is necessary to develop a plan for holding contests, prepare and publish documents, methodological and informational materials for organizing and holding contests, and organize a roundtable on the issues of improving the quality of education.

Today, certain tasks are being carried out in our country to reform the quality of education in form and content, to further improve its legal base, to strengthen its material and technical base, and to increase the effectiveness of the content, forms and methods of education. The creation of new mechanisms in the development of the continuing education system has become a vital necessity of today's globalization processes, and this, in turn, requires the improvement of the effectiveness of the quality of education, its modernization.

In the conditions of modernization of education, it consists of improving its quality, justifying democratization scientifically and pedagogically, determining its priorities, defining pedagogical opportunities, highlighting practical experiences in this regard, and developing general conclusions and recommendations on the subject.

To substantiate the urgency of improving the quality of the continuous education system in our country; determining the priority aspects of modernization of the educational process of higher military educational institutions in the process of globalization; justifying that new innovative approaches used in education are an important tool for improving the quality of education. Today, it is important that the reform of education is not carried out as a departmental project, but that it becomes a political and national task of society.

Creation of scientific-theoretical bases for the development of mechanisms for improving the quality of education of servicemen of engineering troops [3] can be

considered as an important pedagogical problem. The full performance of the duties of the military servicemen of the engineering troops allows the training of professional army representatives consisting of true patriots and qualified specialists of their work. The training of military personnel of the engineering troops in higher military educational institutions is important for fulfilling such a serious, highly responsible and honorable task.

To inculcate the vital and professional skills of military servicemen of the engineering troops on the basis of knowledge [4] in their hearts and minds, to increase their knowledge in harmony with the real social and political changes in the life of our country, to improve their knowledge around us and in the world The higher education system occupies a leading and decisive place in the issues of approaching the ongoing socio-political processes based on our national interests [5], strengthening ideological immunity against internal and external threats.

Since the only way to develop military engineering education today is to speed it up and change its quality, the main problem is the quality of professional training of military specialists.

New approaches to the quality of the specialist's professional training are formed by the latest philosophy of education, the development of pedagogical qualimetry, and the expansion of the experience of quality assessment. At the same time, the scientific formation of the "quality of professional training" phenomenon, which is related to the requirements of the times and the prospects for the development of military engineering, is being carried out in the educational process and practice. The scientific solution requires the creation of a system of improving the quality of education integrated into the family military educational institution.

It should be said that quality theories regarding education as a service have been put into practice. This postulate is typical of general education, especially military education. At the same time, the pedagogical means of improving the quality of education of the engineering troops, by their essence, fully correspond to the essence of the educational process in the higher military educational institution.

It cannot be considered that it has been solved with a deep theoretical study of the quality of education of servicemen of the engineering troops, because the system of improving the quality of education of the servicemen of the engineering troops should be widely introduced.

In conclusion, it can be said that innovative trends in education are sufficiently manifested in the goals, content, and methods of organizing the forms of training of engineering troops with the development of a model with a clear definition of the components of military servicemen of engineering troops.

Infrastructure for military personnel: standardization of the quality of education, optimization of the content of the quality of education, continuous technical updating, quality assessment, corporate standards, scientific and methodological training.

The following approaches can be relied upon in the development of educational programs for improving the quality of education of servicemen of engineering troops of higher military educational institutions: person-oriented, competent, research.

In ensuring the quality of education, active subjects of the education system, all citizens of the country, family and parents community, regional institutions of state power, local self-government bodies, professional and pedagogical team, scientific, cultural, We believe that it is effective for commercial and public institutions to move together.

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